

Global Relevance of Indian Alchemy: A Scientific Renaissance Inspiring Modern Chemistry

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ABSTRACT

The present research work emphasizes on unveiling the rich heritage of the ancient Indian Knowledge System (IKS) from the chemical standpoint, that is, Indian alchemy. It throws light on the different aspects of chemical practices and applications of chemical knowledge in ancient India, that is the practice of alchemy, which is an imperative part of the IKS. Besides this, the study also includes bibliographical analysis of the works of Sir Prafulla Chandra Ray, the Father of Indian Chemistry, and other authentic documents to ascertain the contribution of Indian alchemy towards contemporary Chemistry, including the theoretical basis, practical experimental aspects and areas of applications of contemporary Chemistry.

The vast body of chemical knowledge and practices in the IKS has not only laid the foundation for contemporary Chemistry, a branch of Science, but its holistic approach and emphasis on exploration of indigenous knowledge and locally available natural resources paves way towards ensuring sustainability that has been found to inspire contemporary researchers as has been revealed through the present analytical research. The continuous on-going research on the contributions of Indian alchemy further reflects its growing global significance for addressing sustainability issues over synthetic Chemistry.

This paper finally identifies the features of the chemical practices by Indian alchemists and their significance, and thus, emphasizes on scientific and relevant integration of elements of Indian alchemy and contemporary ideas of Chemistry in order to inspire and provide experiential learning opportunities to young learners with emphasis on interdisciplinarity, sustainability and globalization of Indian indigenous knowledge. Effective integration of Indian alchemy in the form of IKS and contemporary Chemistry is also expected to equip young learners with ideas that focus on the social and environmental impacts of chemical substances and processes and aim towards a global sustainable future.

KEYWORDS: Indian Knowledge System, Indian Alchemy, Contemporary Chemistry, Elements of IKS, Sustainability, Globalization.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Chemistry, often referred to as the Central Science owing to its immense importance compared to the other branches of Science, existed throughout since the formation of Earth and development of life.

Chemistry is that branch of Science which deals with the various forms of matter, their compositions, structures and transformation. People, even in ancient civilizations, had profound practical knowledge on the use of various chemical substances and used technologies that were based on principles which, at modern times, can be related to those of various branches of Chemistry. The rich heritage of chemical knowledge in ancient times can be witnessed from the works of alchemists in India as well as in several other parts of the world.

India has a rich heritage of not only culture and values, but of a structured body of knowledge in diverse fields. Among these, of particular interest is the huge body of scientific knowledge that originated in ancient India and has influenced the entire world at later times.

Ancient Indian Knowledge System (IKS) refers to that body of knowledge which finds its origin in the era of Indus Valley Civilization and the Vedic period and has been transmitted over generations through their practice and applications. Indian alchemy encompasses those aspects of the IKS which are related to the chemical viewpoint.

Several contemporary researchers, including eminent chemists as Sir P.C. Ray, have identified and highlighted the huge contributions of ancient Indian alchemists in the field of chemical understanding and related practices in their works. The principles and concepts of alchemy have influenced and paved way for scientific development at later times. Not only that the basic theoretical and practical aspects of contemporary Chemistry have been found to be guided by alchemical concepts and practices, but also the ancient Indian knowledge of Science and Technology plays a significant role in inspiring modern day research. Thus, it becomes important to analyze the significant features of Indian alchemical practices and their relevance in the present times.

To draw the maximum benefit out of scientific thoughts and discoveries, it is not only important to make young learners aware of the latest advancements, but also their roots so that they might grow up to further contribute to the existing body of knowledge while acknowledging its importance. It, thus, becomes crucial to have a clear idea about the features of the ancient practices of alchemy, and their present implications, in order to ensure effective integration of modern technology with indigenous knowledge, aiming towards a sustainable future, benefitting not only the young learners and contemporary researchers but also to address present issues at global level.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the present research study are as follows:

- To study the practice of alchemy in ancient India.
- To study the contribution of Indian alchemy towards contemporary Chemistry with emphasis on the analysis of the works of Sir P.C. Ray.
- To study the importance of Indian alchemy as an Indian Knowledge System that inspired contemporary chemists.
- To study the implications of Indian alchemy in present-day Chemistry education.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present research work is based on a Qualitative Approach. This qualitative study involved historical and bibliographical research that required an in-depth analysis of historical documents including autobiography of eminent chemist Sir P.C. Ray, historical books, authentic excerpts of medieval texts along with contemporary research articles and review journals. This has been followed by a descriptive analysis of the data collected from different bibliographical sources.

While carrying out the research work, information collected from primary as well as secondary sources have been critically analyzed both internally and externally, followed by systematically evaluating and summarizing the qualitative data to arrive at inferences.

4. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Practice of Alchemy in India

Although India has a rich structured body of knowledge in diverse fields, the present research work, however, is only focused on those aspects of the IKS which are related to the chemical viewpoint, that is, the Indian alchemy.

From detailed analytical study of various historical evidences, a significant development in the chemical practices and applications of chemical knowledge in ancient India has been revealed, besides those occurring in other parts of the world [1-8]. Development in the practice of alchemy in certain regions of the world was brought about by influence of foreign knowledge and culture [1,7,9]. On the other hand, in several other regions world-wide, such as in ancient India, alchemy emerged almost independently and no clear evidence of direct influence from other regions could be found. Sir P.C. Ray, in the second volume of his book 'History of Hindu Chemistry' [3], mentioned that, "...alchemy in India has been developed all along on independent lines" (Ray, 1925, p.133), emphasizing on the indigenous origin of Indian alchemy.

However, there are varied opinions as has been mentioned in a section of a letter by famous chemist, M. Berthelot, to Sir P.C. Ray, as provided in the autobiography of the latter [1],

"I am led to believe that the Indian and Chinese alchemy has come from Greece by the intermediaries of the Syrian Nestorians of the 6th and 8th century of our era." (Ray, 1958, p.93)

A thorough research on several ancient Indian treatises and the reviews on them has, however, led to the conclusion which is in accordance with what had been highlighted by Sir P.C. Ray [2,3,10,11]. Ray, in the first volume of his book 'History of Hindu Chemistry', further mentioned that, the 'dawn of Hindu Alchemy' was during the period of the Vedas and was "*intimately associated with medicinal preparations, metallurgical operations, the technical arts and the belief in the transmutation of metals*", which has been found to corroborate well with several evidences [9-13]. Notably, various remarkable Indian works on Ayurveda and Iatrochemistry from late BCE to early CE such as Charaka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita, when analyzed based on the chemical

standpoint, reflect the growth of chemical knowledge and understanding of their applications even in ancient India [2,4,14-16]. However, the more prominent alchemical development was observed during the medieval period [4,13-16].

Similar to what has been witnessed in other parts of the world, alchemical practices in ancient India has been found to focus more on the applications of chemical knowledge and not much on the theoretical, structural understanding of different forms of matter and their transformations. Also, a comprehensive study and analysis of historical texts and other evidences reflects that not all areas of chemical knowledge developed simultaneously in Indian alchemy. Rather, a systematic pattern has been perceived in the cultivation and growth of Indian alchemy. With each evolving era, further advancement in the already existing body of alchemical knowledge has been observed, with new chemical knowledge being developed in certain other areas, reflecting a continued enhancement in the understanding and skills of the alchemists in varied fields of application such as metallurgy, medicine, cosmetics, etc.

Thus, following a rigorous analysis, it has been found that the historical timeline of practice of alchemy in India and the gradual evolution of the areas of study of the alchemists can be broadly classified in four periods of time, as tabulated in Table 1 [2,10,11,13,16-24]. Table 1 (Timeline of Development of Practice of Alchemy in India) delineates the four periods and the predominant areas of alchemical applications during each period along with the prominent sources of evidence.

Table 1: Timeline of Development of Practice of Alchemy in India

Approximate Time Period	Sources of Evidence	Areas of Alchemical Application
Indus Valley Civilization to Late BCE	Archaeological evidences, knowledge from Yajurveda and Rigveda, other treatises like Charaka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita, accounts of foreign travelers, etc.	Compositions of construction materials Pottery, glass making and extraction and processing of metals Paints and dyes from natural extracts and their use Ayurvedic medicine
Early CE to around 600-700 CE	Varahamihira's Brihatsamhita	Cosmetics and perfumes from different inorganic and organic extracts
	Documentations of Siddha medicinal formulations	Advanced technology for drug delivery
Around 800-1000 CE	8 th century Kashmiri document	Understanding and exploiting the properties of elements
	Rasarnavam	Advanced experimentations – Illustrations on use of apparatus for experimental purposes; chemical experimentations including flame test for metal detection
Around 1000-1600 CE	Rasaratna Samucchaya and other texts on medicine	New metallic combinations with ancient drugs resulting in the formulation of new group of drugs; introduction of poison and psychotropic drugs
	Rasratnakara by Nagarjuna	Metallurgy, metal extraction and purification, and metal works in different parts of the country
	Texts by Chakrapani Datta	Invention of soaps using mustard oil and some alkalies

	Rasopanisada and Tamil texts	Preparation of gun powder mixture and fireworks
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4.2. Contribution of Indian Alchemy towards Contemporary Chemistry

4.2.1. Relevance of Alchemical Knowledge in Contemporary Chemistry through Critical Analysis of the Works of Sir P.C. Ray

Indian alchemy, including the knowledge as well as the infrastructure used by the alchemists, can be well accepted as the foundation for contemporary chemical understanding and research not only in India, but across the world. The importance and rich heritage of the indigenous knowledge system of Indian alchemy has been well reflected in the books ‘History of Hindu Chemistry’ (Volumes I and II) by Sir P.C. Ray [2,3]. Ray, in the aforementioned books, identified various ancient and medieval Indian texts and highlighted the chemical basis of the knowledge shared in those texts. Such alchemical ideas have been found to be largely related to the contemporary chemical practices on critical analysis, as presented in the Tables 2.1 to 2.6 (Table 2: The Alchemical Concepts and Knowledge Highlighted in ‘History of Hindu Chemistry’ (Volumes I and II) and their Relevance in Contemporary Chemistry).

Table 2: The Alchemical Concepts and Knowledge Highlighted in ‘History of Hindu Chemistry’ (Volumes I and II) and their Relevance in Contemporary Chemistry

Table 2.1: Source – Vaiseshika Philosophy by Sage Kanada

Alchemical Concepts	Related Concepts in Contemporary Chemistry
Every individual is an aggregate effect or product of small indivisible particles	The Atomic Theory
Different qualities of different types of substances	States of matter and their properties
Types of objects depending on source	Organic and Inorganic substances

Table 2.2: Source – Vagbhata

Alchemical Concepts	Related Concepts in Contemporary Chemistry
Metallic and mineral preparations to treat diseases – Use of Gold, Silver, Copper, Iron Lead	Medicinal Chemistry
Use of Mercury for medicinal purposes	

Table 2.3: Source – Charaka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita

Alchemical Concepts	Related Concepts in Contemporary Chemistry
Types of Salts, Alkalies	Inorganic Chemistry
Types, Properties and Use of alkalies to neutralize acid	Acid-Alkali Neutralization Reaction (Inorganic Chemistry)

Health issues and various medicinal compositions for their treatment: Mineral and metallic preparations Urine (eight varieties) Powder of pearl compound Tonics, etc.	Medicinal Chemistry
Preparation of alkalis from plant sources Use of alkalis and alkaline caustics for medicinal purposes - For external and internal administration	
Categorization of minerals and other drugs for internal and external administration Concept of the Poisons	
Roasting of iron and other metals	Metallurgy (Inorganic Chemistry)
Rasa (Chyle) and its properties	Chemical properties of blood (Biochemistry)
Chemical compositions of medicines for common diseases like hiccough, cough, or of ear and eye ointment, and even hair dye.	Medicinal and Cosmetic Chemistry

Table 2.4: Source – Rasarnava

Alchemical Concepts	Related Concepts in Contemporary Chemistry
Specialised apparatus for specific purposes	Chemistry laboratory equipment
Flame colour in presence of metals	Inorganic Chemistry
Extraction of metals	Metallurgy

Table 2.5: Source – Chakrapani

Alchemical Concepts	Related Concepts in Contemporary Chemistry
Preparations of Black Sulphide of Mercury, various Copper and Iron compounds, Rust of Iron	Inorganic Chemistry
Preparing soap to be used as depilatory	Cosmetic Chemistry

Table 2.6: Source – Rasaratna Samucchaya

Alchemical Concepts	Related Concepts in Contemporary Chemistry
Construction of apparatus	Chemistry laboratory equipment
Extraction, liquefaction and purification of metals Compositions consisting of more than one metal	Inorganic Chemistry (Metallurgy and Alloy formation)
Mercurials and other metals and minerals for the treatment of diseases Extracts from organic sources as medicine	Medicinal Chemistry (Organic and Inorganic sources of medicine)

Besides these, further elaborations on the chemistry depicted in different alchemical treatises, particularly those during around 1100 CE to 1300 CE, could be found in both the volumes of ‘History of Hindu Chemistry’, which are largely relevant to certain aspects of contemporary study of Chemistry, such as, the concept of atoms and properties of matter, Chemical laboratories and apparatus, chemical reactions and chemical change, and even applications of chemical knowledge in varied fields as medicine, cosmetics and other industries [2,3,16].

4.2.2. Major Contributions of Indian Alchemy towards Development of Contemporary Chemistry and its Applications

As has been analyzed from the works of Sir P.C. Ray and reports on other ancient and medieval evidences [1-4,11,18,19,21-23,25-27], it could be inferred that the alchemical ideas and skills paved way for smooth development of present-day Chemistry, which is a branch of Science, in a number of ways as discussed herein.

4.2.2.1. Theoretical Understanding

- **Concept of atom by Sage Kanada –**

Although the alchemists did not illustrate much about the structure of elements and compounds and associated theoretical concepts, but the idea that matter is made up of small indivisible particles is found in the philosophy put forward by Sage Kanada thousands of years before John Dalton proposed his atomic theory. Sage Kanada named those particles as ‘Anu’ that are comparable to molecules according to modern concept.

- **Properties of matter in Vaiseshika philosophy –**

In the Vaiseshika philosophy of Sage Kanada, mentions have been found on the differences in the properties of substances and that “*quality is closely united with substance*” [2]. A detailed analysis of further elaborations is indicative of the contemporary concept of compositions and states of matter and the differences in properties associated with the corresponding compositions and states.

- **Organic and Inorganic Substances in Rasaratna Samucchaya by Manikyadeva Suri –**

It has been found in several alchemical texts, especially those on medicine, that even during the ancient times, the alchemists had clear conception on the different types of substances and their sources. This provided a preliminary understanding about differences in minerals and plant or animal extracts which has now been scientifically established as inorganic and organic substances respectively.

4.2.2.2. Practical Experimentations

- **Chemical laboratories (Rasasalas) as in Rasaratna Samucchaya –**

Alchemists were skilled experimentalists. Illustrations of well-planned ‘Rasasalas’ or laboratories used by the alchemists have been found in a number of texts including Rasaratna Samucchaya. Besides archaeological evidences of different apparatus used by the alchemists for specialized purposes like distillation, trituration, etc. have also been found. Such planned ‘Rasasala’ used by the alchemists are highly relevant if one aims to trace back the origin of initial chemistry laboratories and the planning and arrangements of the necessary equipment and apparatuses in a laboratory.

- **Laboratory-based chemical reactions as portrayed in Rasarnava and Rasaratnakara –**

The Indian alchemists had developed knowledge on the chemical properties of various substances and their reactions (e.g., extensive laboratory-based experimental reactions were conducted by Nagarjuna). From such evidences it could be realized that the experimental understanding of the alchemists paved way for more precise laboratory-based chemical reactions conducted by contemporary chemists, which further led to development of synthetic chemistry.

4.2.2.3. Applications of Chemistry

- **Foundational knowledge on the impacts of various organic and inorganic substances in human life from medieval treatises on materia medica –**

The much advanced medicinal knowledge of the alchemists included those about how certain organic as well as inorganic substances such as metals or minerals can prove to be beneficial for humans. Illustrations of various drugs, their compositions and their beneficial role in treatment of diseases are obtained from several texts and treatises of medieval India, that largely benefitted the further development of medicinal Chemistry in the contemporary times.

- **Understanding toxicity of elements from Charaka Samhita, Rasaratna Samucchaya and other treatises –**

Clear mentions about the adverse effects of specific elements and the ways to treat the consequences are also noticed in various alchemical treatises. For example, metallic/mineral or herbo-metallic formulations of drugs including iron and mercury have been found to be marked as contraindicated for pregnant women and children in Rasaratna Samucchaya. Such contraindications highlighted by Indian alchemists in various texts are highly relevant even today from the medicinal standpoint.

- **Technological ideas for advanced research on modern medicines : Use of Bhasmas in Charaka Samhita –**

The concept of using ‘Bhasmas’ of metals, that is, metal particles that have been reduced to extremely small size, as drugs for treatment of ailments have been mentioned in Charaka Samhita and other texts from the period of Indian Alchemy. This concept is related to the technology of drug delivery in modern medical science where nanostructures of drug molecules have proved to result in improved drug availability within the body besides reducing the effects of drug toxicity.

- **Identifying the importance of Chemistry in daily life from the goal of alchemical practices –**

Indian alchemists had extensive knowledge on the beneficial use of various chemical substances in our daily life. The common examples of such applications are those for human beauty and hygiene. Although in the initial practices of Alchemy, in ancient India, various cosmetics, perfumes, hair dyes etc. as well as soaps have been found to be derived from natural extracts, various treatises of the medieval period provided detailed discussion on the composition of such formulations reflecting on the chemical aspects. At later times, prominent ayurvedic scholars reported more refined procedures for preparation of cosmetic items, as well as soft soaps, which highlighted the importance of Chemistry in ensuring not only health, but also beauty and hygiene of humans, during the contemporary studies.

- **Foundation of Industrial Chemistry –**

Besides those discussed above, the knowledge and skills developed by the alchemists in certain fields paved way for development of Industrial Chemistry, some examples of which are tabulated in Table 3 (Table 3: Some Prominent Areas of Alchemical Knowledge Promoting the Development of Industrial Chemistry).

Table 3: Some Prominent Areas of Alchemical Knowledge Promoting the Development of Industrial Chemistry

Areas of Alchemical Study	Fields of Study in Industrial Chemistry Developed at Later Time
Extraction and refinement of metals; Preparing alloys of metals such as lead, tin, copper and iron.	Metallurgy
Provided roots for Iatrochemistry - Discovering medicines for diseases	Medicinal Chemistry
Cloth dyeing, making varnishes for water-proofing of cloth, tanning leather materials	Textile Chemistry
Preparation of important chemicals such as paints, dyes, or inorganic chemicals as acids, alkalies, etc. that are used in laboratories or other industrial preparations	Manufacturing of Chemicals

Thus, it is realized that the contribution of the Indian alchemists towards the contemporary Chemistry is not just constrained within the knowledge developed in various fields of application, but also in the development of theoretical and laboratory-based experimental aspects of Chemistry.

4.3. Importance of Indian Alchemy as an Indian Knowledge System that Inspired Contemporary Chemists

Ancient Indian Knowledge System (IKS), more specifically, the Indian alchemy has been unveiled as a huge, structured body of scientific knowledge that has not only inspired contemporary chemists, but has become more relevant in the present world as discussed herein.

Interconnection of chemical processes with nature and human life –

The major difference between the IKS and modern Chemistry is that IKS considers every chemical process holistically taking into account its interconnection with nature as well as the impact on humans. The alchemists in ancient as well as medieval India largely relied on natural sources for the chemical substances used by them and even for preparing the medicinal formulations [28]. While on the other hand, the principles of contemporary Chemistry largely deal with individual elements and compounds and their properties, with focus on quantitative precisions.

Exploration of Indian indigenous knowledge : Inspiration for contemporary chemists –

Over the years, IKS has inspired several great researchers, particularly chemists, and has influenced their research and thoughts extensively. Of special mention is Sir P.C. Ray, the Father of Indian Chemistry, who studied the historical development of chemical ideas and knowledge in India and has elaborated his findings in his landmark books History of Hindu Chemistry (Vol I and Vol II) [2,3]. Ray, in one of his essays [29], mentioned:

“In that morning of ancient history, the world looked forward to India for light and guidance, for knowledge of the accurate sciences such as algebra and chemistry as shown in my History of Hindu Chemistry, for personal and social purity, for sacrifice and abstinence, for plain living and high thinking.”

The knowledge and practice of Chemistry in ancient India fostered sustainable living of the people, which largely inspired contemporary research that focused on improving the quality of life and livelihood of the people globally.

From the analysis of the discussions in the autobiography of Sir P.C. Ray [1], the significance of IKS, particularly in the context of chemical applications, is largely due to the following characteristics :

- **Indigenous knowledge**
- **Involving use of locally available resources**
- **Sustainability**

IKS, specifically Indian alchemy, not just inspired research and innovation in Chemistry during the period of Sir P.C. Ray, but continued to inspire young researchers over generations. With advancing scientific technology, the contributions of alchemists were validated scientifically and considered for application in modern scenarios.

Some prominent examples that can be cited to depict the ever-growing importance of indigenous Indian alchemical knowledge in contemporary Chemistry research and development are as follows :

i. Works of Sir P.C. Ray [1,30] –

- Research on basic food items like onion and garlic and other plants to understand their medicinal values.
- Establishment of the **Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works in 1901, the first pharmaceutical company of India**, for large scale manufacturing of indigenous products, including ayurvedic formulations, to emphasize on the sustainable chemical properties and effectiveness of indigenous practices.
- Production of Copperas (Hydrated Ferrous Sulphate) using scrap iron from local market.
- Preparation of Phosphate of Soda and Superphosphate of Lime from bones of cattle.
- Preparing powdered form of Phosphate of Calcium, which is prescribed as a nerve tonic, from burnt bones.
- Ayurvedic preparations of extracts of medicinal plants like Kalmegh, Kurchi, Vasaka and also, aqua Ptychotis, etc.

ii. Establishment of other indigenous chemical laboratories and companies –

Inspired by the indigenous knowledge of our country and with emphasis on the importance of Ayurveda, several researchers came up to pioneer large scale production of ayurvedic formulations as depicted in Table 4 (Table 4: List of Some Prominent Ayurveda-Based Companies), which reflects growing public awareness on the beneficial role of India's indigenous knowledge system for sustainable living [31]. Such companies have been found to have acquired recognition in the global market over the years.

Table 4: List of Some Prominent Ayurveda-Based Companies

Name of the Company	Founder	Year of Establishment	Products
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Dabur	S.K. Burman	1884	Current ayurvedic products include those for health care, hair care, oral care, and other herbal food and beverages, home care products, etc.
Sadhana Aushadhalaya	Jogesh Chandra Ghosh	1914	450 types of ayurvedic drugs in the early period, which decreased significantly at later times
Baidyanath	Pandit Ramnarayan Sharma	1917	Ayurvedic medicines and other health care products
Himalaya Drug Company	Mohammad Manal	1930	Ayurvedic medicines
Patanjali Ayurved	Ramdev and Balkrishna	2006	Ayurvedic medicines and herbal items for personal care, nutrition, home care.

iii. More latest research such as –

- Analysis of the traditional medicines of the alchemists. For example, SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) analysis of the ‘Bhasmas’ used as medicines in the Siddha tradition proved the presence of nanoparticles in the formulation [20].
- Extensive research on Indian medicinal plants, shift towards use of organic fertilizers, etc [32,33].

This indicated that the applications of Indian indigenous knowledge system are highly relevant in the present-day world. Also in the present circumstances, the effectiveness and significance of indigenous ‘ayurvedic’ products could be understood from the latest technology-based research on their chemical basis.

In the post-alchemical period, with the growing expertise of the synthetic chemists and a better understanding of the individual elements and compounds, an increased use of synthetic chemical compounds has been witnessed in varied fields such as in fertilizers, pesticides, medicines, beauty products, etc. which had harmful consequences on human health and environment. Thus, with the growing global concerns on sustainability issues, it has become more important to consider the qualitative impacts of any chemical process, both on nature and humans. Not only that, IKS has resourceful strategies and information, which if explored appropriately, can help to move away from the harmful effects of synthetic drugs, cosmetics, fertilizers and other chemicals that the world comes across in everyday life, as evidenced from the growing preference of the people in India as well as worldwide for Ayurveda and other ancient Indian sustainable practices.

4.4. Implications of Indian Alchemy in the Present-Day Chemistry Education

As has been unveiled through the earlier discussions, having foundation on the rich alchemical knowledge, Chemistry gradually enlarged its boundaries with continuous advancements in scientific research and discoveries, enlightening and benefitting humans with diverse knowledge. This highlights the pivotal role of Chemistry and the need for advancing Chemistry education, in raising scientific awareness and literacy among masses, and consequently, addressing several global challenges.

4.4.1. Relevant Integration of Indian Knowledge System within Chemistry Education

Every country has its own future aspirations that can be best realized if the knowledge about the journey of its development from past to the present is clearly known. The local needs and demands of every country cumulatively contribute to the global needs, which can be best addressed if considered from local perspectives.

Modern Chemistry education, thus, must incorporate the visions that significantly shaped Chemistry pedagogical discourse in India. Sir P.C. Ray, the Father of Indian Chemistry, had long ago highlighted the need for integration of indigenous knowledge, promoting research-based learning and linking academia with industry in his autobiography ‘Autobiography of a Bengali Chemist’, suggesting that Chemistry should enable everyone to flourish their potential towards positive social contribution [1].

To reflect such views in Chemistry education, scientific integration of the chemical knowledge and principles of Indian alchemy with the existing educational structure can prove to be immensely beneficial.

Global Relevance of Indian Alchemy: A Scientific Renaissance Inspiring Modern Chemistry

Some of the major issues having global impacts, that have also been highlighted in the reports of the United Nations, include those related to health and well-being, food, water, climate change and sustainability, and Chemistry can play an important role in addressing such global issues.

If the young learners and researchers are acquainted with the indigenous knowledge system of Indian alchemy and its contribution towards development of fundamental concepts of contemporary Chemistry and its branches, it is possible to provide an education that would enable them

- to put the knowledge of Chemistry to practice in local contexts
- to develop the idea on how to address daily life problems with locally available resources
- to realize the merits of employing practices mentioned in IKS over synthetic chemical materials to ensure sustainability, among others.

The importance and rich heritage of the Indian Knowledge System from the stand-point of Chemistry, as depicted in Figure 1 (Figure 1: Features of the chemical practices in IKS), has been found to be highlighted by Sir P.C. Ray long ago as has been already discussed [1]. But, there was no significant effort to acquaint young learners with such knowledge structure for long.

Figure 1: Features of the chemical practices in IKS.

The existing system of Chemistry education largely include theoretical and practical discussions on various concepts and principles of contemporary Chemistry besides certain dedicated chapters illustrating the applications of Chemistry in human life, but fail to connect with the local needs and use of locally available sources of chemical substances. It is hereby implied to incorporate elements and principles of IKS, particularly Indian alchemy, that are relevant and scientifically associated with any concept of contemporary Chemistry, not in an isolated way, but rather through harmonious synthesis that would help learners and researchers understand the significance of the ancient Indian body of knowledge.

Figure 2: Incorporation of elements of IKS (Indian alchemy) through relevant scientific integration.

Thus, as depicted in Figure 2 (Figure 2: Incorporation of elements of IKS (Indian alchemy) through relevant scientific integration), the interrelations between the different concepts and principles of contemporary Chemistry, the relevant elements of IKS and their applications and impact in human life need to be clear and precise throughout the process of Chemistry education at all levels.

4.4.2. Implications in Learning of Chemistry

Based on critical analysis of various proposed educational models for teaching-learning of Chemistry, it is believed that the incorporation of concepts of IKS, especially Indian alchemy, besides mentions of latest advancements in the applications of Chemistry would benefit the learners with certain significant implications as discussed herein.

- **Experiential learning** – Enabling the learners to identify and deal with real life problems using appropriate knowledge about the chemical characteristics of various substances around them and associated concepts and principles of Chemistry.
- **Interdisciplinary approach** – The learners are expected to develop holistic outlook on how Chemistry influences other fields of study. For example, an introduction to what Sir P.C. Ray mentioned in his autobiography [1], “I also knew full well that our Kavirajas (Ayurvedic physicians) used many metallic preparations of which an account is given in Udoychand Dutt’s *Materia Medica of the Hindus*.” and supplementary information would enlighten learners about the interdisciplinary approach of scientific study prevalent in ancient India.
- **Considering environmental and social impacts** – Making learners and young researchers aware of the need to consider environmental and social impacts of various chemicals and chemical practices. Indian alchemical knowledge and practices largely reflected on such aspects as already discussed.
- **Focus on sustainability** – Enriching the learners with knowledge and skill to ensure sustainable development which is an issue of utmost importance in present global scenario. IKS is particularly important in this respect as it focuses on applications of Chemistry in a sustainable way.
- **Globalization of indigenous knowledge** – Helping learners develop the ability to integrate modern technology with indigenous knowledge promoting futuristic innovations with global outlook.
- **Focusing on ethical considerations** – Laboratory-based or even, large-scale industrial synthesis of chemical substances are associated with inherent risks and production of hazardous by-products. IKS provided approaches of chemical practices that aim towards a greener pathway with environmental protection and social responsibility in consideration and can help learners relate to the modern branch of Green Chemistry.

5. CONCLUSION

The present research work indeed throws light on how Chemistry and chemical practices, from the era of Indian Alchemy to that of contemporary Science, inspired young researchers who worked to make use of the chemical knowledge to improve the quality of life of people.

The research reflected on the contributions of Indian alchemists and thereafter, the contemporary research of great Indian chemists, namely Sir P.C. Ray, that unveiled the chemical significance and present-day relevance of the Indian indigenous knowledge system. Through bibliographical analysis, the research could arrive at the conclusion that Chemistry, besides having an indispensable role in human life, can also pave way for a sustainable art of living through the alchemical ideas that integrate chemical knowledge with human life and nature.

The research also reflected on the views of Sir P.C. Ray on the significance of Indian Knowledge System, that might be integrated to enrich Chemistry education. Sir P.C. Ray highlighted that an understanding of the Indian indigenous knowledge structure can help to make the knowledge of Chemistry relatable in local contexts, besides mentioning about the importance of practices mentioned in IKS towards ensuring sustainability. Thus, the works of Sir Ray, although not explicitly, underline the need for integration of elements of IKS in Chemistry education as could be inferred through the analytical research.

The present study, thus, leads to the conclusion that effective integration of Indian alchemy in the form of IKS and contemporary ideas of Chemistry is expected to ensure interdisciplinary, experiential and effective learning of the learners and equip them with ideas that focus on the social and environmental impacts of chemical substances and processes and aim towards a global sustainable future. This is expected to bring about a pedagogical shift in the learning of Chemistry, making it more relevant and interesting to the young learners who would be motivated to explore the subject further for the benefit of mankind.

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